

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF IRON (III) IONS WITH THE HELP OF GOSSYPOL AZOBIRIKS

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Abstract. *The article provides information on the use of a nitrogen-containing gossypol derivative as a reagent for iron ions (+3) in the presence of a universal buffer solution. The optimal conditions for the complex formation of the reagent with metal ions are selected. The effect of extraneous interfering ions has been studied. A technique for the spectrophotometric determination of iron ions (+3) is proposed, which is applied to the analysis of a sample of natural water.*

Keywords: *gossypol, a nitrogen-containing derivative of gossypol, analytic reagent, iron, spectrophotometric method, complexation.*

Introduction. The development of science and technology and production requires the development of high-sensitivity, expressive, selective and simple methods for the determination of elements. Complex natural mineral samples are also important due to the selectivity of most photometric methods, which allow elemental determination without chemical separation. Currently, as a result of the development of heavy industry and technology, in areas where the level of poisoning of environmental objects is increasing, as well as in order to control the amount of iron in a living organism, it is one of the urgent issues to determine it by selective and highly sensitive methods. In this study, the effect of the nitrogen-fixing product of gossypol (GAX-2) on trivalent iron ion was analyzed by spectrophotometric method.

Review of literature

The use of reagents consisting of natural compounds containing functional analytical groups can not only reduce the detection limit of the object of analysis, but also significantly reduce or completely eliminate the background effect of macrocomponents, and increase the reproducibility and sensitivity of the analysis method, as well as the desired form of the analysis elements. allows to distinguish from other chemical modifications without changing the existing state. Among the polyphenolic compounds, gossypol meets the requirements of the same analysis with its chemical structure and properties.

Gossypol and its nitrogen-containing derivatives are compounds with a wide range of physiological activity, and now 3% gossypol liniment against viral diseases, 3% megosin ointment against herpes diseases, and other drugs based on them are widely used in medicine [1-2]. Taking this into account, this research work is devoted to the creation of new selective analytical reagents for the spectrophotometric determination and quantitative control of heavy and toxic metal ions in various natural samples, industrial effluents, ores and some biological samples using gossypol azo derivatives which is one of the urgent problems of the field of environmental protection. Several spectrophotometric determination methods have been developed for the analysis of iron from minerals and natural samples using analytical reagents, but these methods do not fully meet the analysis requirements, if one of the available methods has low sensitivity, the other will not have sufficient selectivity, so in chemical analysis, much attention is paid to the identification of

selective analytical reagents [1-5]. Because it is very difficult to create analytical reagents with high selectivity. Therefore, in most cases, group reagents are used for the detection of ions, the analysis conditions are changed, for example, the solution medium (pN), the composition of the buffer mixture is changed, or masking procedures are used[5-7].

Taking this into account, in this study, the authors studied the reactions of gossypol azo derivatives with electron-donating properties, i.e. (GAX-2) reagent and some iron (III) ions, and their spectrophotometric characteristics were studied [8-10].

Research methodology

For the research, chemical reagents, as well as materials and equipment, qualified as chemically pure (k.t.) and analytically pure (a.u.t.) were used. Preparation of working solutions: for the research, it was prepared from the iron salt standard solution (a.u.t.), which forms a complex with the nitrogen derivative of technical gossypol (GAX-2) reagent. Newly prepared solutions of alkali and mineral acids and organic solvents were used. The light absorption coefficients of the solutions were measured in the spectrophotometer "UV/Vis spectrophotometer Optizen III" (South Korea), in cuvettes with a thickness of 1 cm ($l=1$). The pH/mV/ TEMP Meter R 25 pH meter of the solutions was monitored.

Determination method: spectrophotometric method was used to study the chemistry of complex formation reactions of iron metal ions with GAX-2 reagent, the optimal conditions for the reaction of complex formation of iron metal ions with nitrogen derivatives of gossypol were determined, the initial absorption spectrum of the complex, the solution environment and other parameters were also studied.

Analysis and results

The nitrogenous derivative of gossypol is a dark red, amorphous natural biologically active substance that dissolves in some organic solvents. In addition to the presence of various polar groups in the composition of the gossypol molecule, the naphthalene residue also contains groups that cause hydrophobicity and affect its solubility.

The systematic nomenclature name of the reagent gossypol azo derivative - (GAH-2) [(1Z,1'E) - (8,8'- diformyl - 1,1',6,6',7,7'- hexahydroxy - 5, 5'-Diisoroaryl - 3,3'- dimethyl - [2,2' - binaphthalene] -4,4'-diyl)]. The chemical structural formula of bis(diazene-2,1-diyl)] bis(ethane-2,1-diyl) bis(hydrosulfate) is as follows:

Figure 1. Structural formula of GAH-2 reagent.

GAH-2 reagent is a reddish-brown powder. The optimal condition of the analysis was determined for studying the complex formation reaction of iron ion with gossypol azo derivative. Absorption spectra of the solution under the selected optimal conditions were obtained. The

absorption spectrum of the reagent was obtained against distilled water. First, the optimal light filter of the complex solution was selected.

Figure 2. Dependence of optical density of Fe(III) ion complex with GAH-2 reagent on wavelength. $\lambda_{Fe(III)}=490$.

According to the results presented in (Figure 2), GAH-2 of Fe(III) ions showed the highest optical density at a wavelength of $\lambda_{Fe(III)}=490$.

The pH value of the solution being analyzed spectrophotometrically is maintained uniformly by using appropriate buffer solutions or sufficient amounts of acid or alkali. Reagent and metal ion concentration also affect the value of optical density. Taking this into account, at first, the optimal conditions for the reaction of complex formation were determined. The dependence of the optical density on the pH of the solution was studied, because one of the important conditions for the implementation of the spectrophotometric reaction is the environment of the solution.

Figure 2. Graph of dependence of Fe(III) ion complex formation with GAH-2 on optimum environment.

Optizen-III spectrophotometer (South Korea) used universal buffer solutions with different pH values for the analysis of the complex formation of Gossypol azocompound with iron (III) ion. It was found that the selected favorable conditions are specific for the studied metal ion. The main reason for this is the nature of the reagent and metal ions. Of course, in order to study the

dependence of the optical density value on the solution environment, buffer solutions with different compositions and values were used.

According to the research results, it was found that it is possible to use a universal buffer solution with $\text{pHFe(III)}=4.4$. It was found that the yield of the complex formed by Fe(III) with GAH-2 depends on the order of pouring the components.

The ratio of component moles of the complex formed by Fe(III) with GAH-2 was determined. Analytical methods used in the determination of complex compounds and determination of their mole ratios in this study were determined by the isomolar series method, Asmus's straight line method, and spectrophotometric methods.

Figure 3. Graph of determination of complex composition of Fe(III) ion with GAH-2 using Isomolar series method.

The ratio of component moles of the Fe(III) ion complex with GAH-2 was determined using Asmus' straight line method and confirmed the results obtained by the isomolar series method. In order to graphically determine the stoichiometric ratios of the affected components, a graph of dependence of $(\ell/V)n$ on $1/A$ was created.

This relationship represents a straight line only for the true value of n . Determination of iron ions from artificial mixtures was carried out using the determined optimal conditions. The obtained results are presented in the table below.

Results of determination of Fe(III) ions from the composition of the artificial mixture with GAH-2 ($n=5$, $P=0.95$)

Solution content mkg	Fe ³⁺ included, mkg	A	Fe ³⁺ found, mkg X _i	S	S _r	$\bar{X} \pm \Delta X$
K ⁺ , Na ⁺ , NH ₄ ⁺ , Cl ⁻ , Br ⁻ , SO ₄ ²⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ (1:500); Al ³⁺ , Ca ²⁺ , Mg ²⁺ , PO ₄ ³⁻ , NO ₂ ⁻ (1:100); Bi ³⁺ , Co ²⁺ , Fe ²⁺ (1:1).	20,0	0,1243 0,1234 0,1236 0,1228 0,1258	19,56	0,192	0,010	19,56±0,238

Conclusions:

Thus, we can come to the following conclusions:

- A new spectrophotometric method for determining iron using Gossippo azo derivative was developed.
- optimal conditions for forming a complex of the reagent with iron (+3) were selected.
- the effect of foreign ions was studied.
- when this spectrophotometric detection method was used to determine iron ions from artificial mixtures, it was found that the relative standard deviation value of sr was 0.010.

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